

School Culture, Work Values, And Work Engagement: A Structural Equation Model On Personaleffectiveness Of Basic Education Private School Teachers

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Abstract

This study determined the best fit model for the personal effectiveness of basic education private school teachers in region XI based on school culture, work values, and work engagement. In this study, a stratified, random sample of 400 respondents was used to test the structural equation model (SEM). Data were obtained from respondents using a series of modified survey questionnaires that were validated for content validity and reliability in an electronic survey using Google Forms. This was accomplished by emailing the aforementioned Google Forms to the school heads' email addresses. When their teachers responded, the responses were instantly transmitted to the researcher in excel format. Further, this study used a quantitative descriptive and causal approach of research. The results of the study, which used mean, standard deviation, Pearson product-moment correlation, and structural equation model (SEM) as statistical tools, revealed that when conferring basic education private school teachers in Region XI, the results of all variables, school culture, work values, work engagement, and personal effectiveness were high. Moreover, a significant relationship existed between these variables. Work values and work engagement are significant predictors of personal effectiveness. Out of five generated models, Model 5 significantly explained the personal effectiveness of basic education private school teachers with work values through indicators core values, work environments, work interactions, work activities, and school culture with indicators professional collaboration, affiliative collegiality, and self-determination/efficacy. It is the most parsimonious model as it successfully passed all the conventions of a reasonable fit.

Keywords: education, school culture, work values, work engagement, personal effectiveness, structural equation model, Philippines

INTRODUCTION

Personal effectiveness is a universal need (Hewitt, 2017). When left unaddressed, an absence of personal effectiveness can make a repeating situation or condition that causes another problem that worsens the first problem. If we are not effective personally, it can spill into our own lives and influence our work-life balance. Furthermore, this is an across-the-country issue where personal effectiveness can affect one's capacity to work profitably, continuing the cycle (Little, 2017).

This study on personal effectiveness plays an integral part in boosting an individual's total capacity to do numerous jobs and activities in school, business, athletics, and life endeavors, according to Sanyal and Fatima (2016). It teaches people the practical, straightforward skills and tactics they need to succeed in all aspects of life. Personal effectiveness appears as the most significant predictor of self-motivation, impact on objectives, and aspirations, according to Walawalkar (2015). Furthermore, it refers to using all of your talents, and energy to achieve a life goal or set of goals. Many people want to improve their personal effectiveness but don't know where to begin. Hence, teachers should use all their abilities (Osborn, 2019).

Moreover, unhealthy school culture can indicate personal ineffectiveness, as Vos, Westhuizen, Mentz, and Ellis (2012). Finding the school atmosphere is a significant part of creating personal effectiveness. In addition, to increment or change personal effectiveness, there's a need to take time and reflect to see where at present it is. A few plans to expand this may incorporate distinguishing own work and reflecting if it is right now inside the arrangement of the work (Jane, 2013).

The literature has indicated the link of the personal effectiveness of teachers to other variables. Work values are related to how employees perform their jobs principally and promote personal effectiveness (Belyn, 2020). They consistently accomplish more work and do it more quickly than those who lack work values

because they don't stop until the task at hand is completed. Likewise, employees' work engagement to organizations has a significant impact on performance, just as personal effectiveness does (Ajibade & Ayinla, 2014). Darolia, Darolia, and Kumari (2010) noted that high work engagement occurrences have likewise demonstrated to profoundly identify with effective execution related to personal effectiveness. With this, the environment of a school, or its culture, significantly affects teachers' day-to-day experiences in the profession and has a significant impact on itself (Tonissen, 2015).

Further, Karim, Choudhary, and Latif (2019) stated, studies on the influence of work values on employees' effectiveness are needed to improve personal effectiveness. Likewise, work engagement is one of the numerous approaches to support employee work satisfaction. Focusing on employee engagement encourages you to make a positive working environment culture that drives work achievement (Shenoy & Echil, 2018).

Basically, this study investigates the relationship between variables, school culture, work values, and work engagement to personal effectiveness, filling the existing gap identified in the literature review. This is to concentrate and to examine the impact of these independent variables- school culture, work values, work engagement to the dependent variable- personal effectiveness critically. Further, no available studies highlight the combined influence of school culture, work values, and work engagement on the personal effectiveness of teachers, specifically in private schools. Literature has focused on the individual influence of the variables on the personal effectiveness of teachers. Thus, this study will be conducted to find a structural equation model on the personal effectiveness of teachers.

Research Objectives

This study aimed to determine what model best fits the personal effectiveness of basic education private school teachers. Specifically, it dealt with the following objectives: Assess the level of a school culture of basic education as perceived by private school teachers in terms of Professional Collaboration; Affiliative Collegiality; and Self-Determination/Efficacy. Ascertain the level of work values of basic education private school teachers in terms of Core Values; Work Environments; Work Interactions; and Work Activities. Describe the level of work engagement of basic education private school teachers in terms of Vigor; Dedication; and Absorption. Assess the level of personal effectiveness of basic education private school teachers in terms of: Self-disclosure; Openness to feedback; and Perceptiveness. Determine the significant relationship of: School Culture and Personal Effectiveness of Basic Education Private School Teachers; Work Values and Personal Effectiveness of Basic Education Private School Teachers; and Work Engagement and Personal Effectiveness of Basic Education Private School Teachers. Determine which exogenous variable/s significantly influence the personal effectiveness of basic education private school teachers. Lastly, determine the model that best fits the personal effectiveness of basic education private school teachers.

Hypothesis

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance that there is no significant relationship between school culture and personal effectiveness, work values and personal effectiveness, and work engagement and personal effectiveness; that school culture, work values, and work engagement do not significantly influence personal effectiveness; that there is no model that best fits personal effectiveness.

LITERATURE REVIEW

School Culture

School culture contains knowledge, beliefs, art, morals, laws, norms, customs, and other skills (Yusof, Osman, & Noor, 2016). Also, it generally alludes to the beliefs, observations, connections, manners, and composed and unwritten standards that shape and impact each part of how a school functions. However, the term also includes increasingly solid issues, for example, students' physical and passionate well-being of students, the efficiency of study halls and open spaces, or how much a school grasps and celebrates racial, ethnic, phonetic, or social assorted variety (Greco, Hascher, & Marcin, 2013).

Normally, schools will have a unique culture formed through interactions among the school community, including administrators, teachers, staff, parents, students, and the local community. Each school community, directly and indirectly, will contribute to some extent in forming a school culture; however, it is not formed in a short period. It will take a long time to establish and develop a culture that once permeated and animated by its community (McLeod, 2012).

As stated, school culture has been demonstrated to be a moderately solid and consistently reliably perceptive factor among the numerous elements influencing the degree to which educators are content with their jobs. It might be that school culture influences school effectiveness legitimately, additionally using the impact of teachers' work fulfilment (Treptharan & Tayiam, 2014),

In improving the country's educational sector, Monsanto (2016) has contended that transformations should begin inside the school's way of life. Making a solid and positive culture in school can realize improvement with its procedures in accomplishing objectives. The book, *How to Create a Culture of Achievement in Your School and Classroom* by Fisher, Frey & Pumpian (2012) indicates positive school culture empowers more prominent exertion and efficiency, improves joint collegial effort, underpins fruitful change and improvement endeavors, fabricates duty and distinguishing proof of students and teachers with your school and intensifies vitality and inspiration of staff individuals and students.

Moreover, in the book, *Creating a Learning Environment: An Educational Leader's Guide to Managing School Culture* by Brucato (2005), he shared that without a solid culture, all endeavors and procedures made by the individuals won't function admirably. The three major indicators of solid school culture are professional collaboration where individuals cooperate and share data, affiliative collegiality, where there is a feeling of having a place and passionate help from every part, and self-determination/efficacy where partners feel as though they have control of their fates or do they see themselves as defenseless casualties of the framework, as indicated by Wagner (2006).

Professional collaboration is the first indicator which is characterized as educators who work freely to accomplish shared objectives connected to the motivation behind learning for all, wherein individuals are considered commonly responsible. They further expressed that collaboration can manufacture solid students and teachers (Perez, 2017). It allows educators to talk about students' reasoning and learning, which improves the instructor's professional improvement. It will assist teachers with reflecting upon and further building up their aptitudes and comprehension of systems while making them responsible for making changes to their education practice. Shared teacher professional development underpins instructors to make substantive and continued changes to their classroom practice by giving time and structure to progressing joint effort concentrated on student learning. Through professional collaboration, teachers' capacity to utilize classroom procedures increments (Dyer, 2013),

The second indicator for school culture is *affiliative collegiality*. *Affiliative collegiality* and collegial relationships depict how school individuals interface and care for each other. School culture is multifaceted, with collegial connections being one part that affects school culture. Culture is a mind-boggling system in a school, making it complex (Glover, 2015). The communications and relations of the school individuals that make up the school association is associated with the school's way of life (Buchanan, 2012). Collegiality happens in an assortment of settings on the school site.

The third indicator of school culture is *self-determination/efficacy*. *Self-determination/efficacy* assumes a significant job in effective learning (Ryan & Deci 2013). Being ready to act self-determinedly is helpful for scholastic accomplishment, positive classroom working, and students' mental prosperity (Jang, Reeve, Ryan, & Kim, 2009). Teachers can effectively utilize self-sufficiency steady procedures in class to encourage self-determined inclusion (Chatzisarantis & Hagger, 2009). As cited by Moesgarrd (2013), the idea of self-efficacy was initially created by Bandura (1995). Its idea of self-efficacy surveys one's center conviction of having the ability to accomplish one's close-to-home objectives by one's behavior. Self-efficacy convictions have been demonstrated to be reliable indicators of conduct results, for example, performance (Ouweneel, LeBlanc, & Schaufeli, 2013). Self-efficacy convictions have been indeed identified with inspiration and commitment,

leading to a more prominent undertaking association. Having important objectives and plans to seek after objectives will probably bring about more elevated commitment.

Work Values

Work values are the subset of your convictions and thoughts identified with your occupation or employment. These center standards are a significant piece of what your identity is. They incorporate things like trustworthiness, administration, a sense of pride, regard for other people, harmony, and achievement (McKay, 2018).

In addition, work values are the mindfulness, emotional wants, needs of individuals, wants of societies that manage their behavior towards work (Pandey & Sharma, 2012). It makes a lot of objectives that an individual looks for from a situation which assumes a crucial job in one's professional growth and professional improvement (Liu & Lei, 2012). The satisfactory results that people hope to accomplish or ought to be achieved through their commitment, inclusion, and active cooperation in work activities (Frieze, Olson, Murell, & Selvan, 2006). It also drives individuals' inspiration to seek after certain undertakings and add to the accomplishment of vision and mission in an institution.

In the academe, positive work values produce results from the learners that continue the work progress and mental improvement of the students through quality instructing in higher education which genuinely matters for student learning results (Hénard & Roseveare, 2012). Teachers serve an excellent example of conduct and inspirational disposition that drives students towards effective direction and occasions of their school life. Keeping up and exhibiting positive work values among educators would likewise give a clear model on the genuine substance of professionalism and integrity. The way educators deliver lessons and oversee classroom circumstances are a portion of the components that may add to the learners' general learning and advancement. These are being assessed occasionally to assemble a few information and data that will fill in as the reason for consistent improvement of the institution.

Work values can be characterized as many attributes and practices that mirror an individual's convictions, qualities, dispositions, and practices toward work (Park & Hill, 2016). Hence, setting up an instructive premise and condition for students to consider word-related hardworking attitudes and further create employability aptitudes. To this end, research to build up a brief proportion of hardworking value characteristics would give a helpful apparatus to improve hardworking value guidance.

The first indicator of work values in the study is *core values*. *Core values* form the foundation on which an establishment is manufactured. To be maintained, they should be actualized over the whole organization, known by workers, and alluded to through the decision-making process. At the point when utilized accurately, core values can give various advantages to an organization. Common core corporate values incorporate responsibility, duty, advancement, trust, and respect. Each should help the structure of an organization and be shown in the day-by-day activities and interchanges both internally and externally (Osborn, 2019).

The second indicator of the independent variable work values is the *work environment*. The *work environment* can be characterized as the surrounding wherein individuals work, incorporating physical setting, work profile, culture, and economic situation. Every perspective is inter-connected and impacts personnel by large execution and efficiency. The nature of the workforces' work environment condition most affects their degree of motivation, consequently performance (Ikechukwu, Achori, Achori, & Okechukwu, A. 2019). Furthermore, workers will consistently have contended when they feel that their quick condition states match their commitments (Farh, Seo, & Tesluk, 2020). It stated that the *work environment* condition in which personnel work decides if the organization will prosper. The working environment condition comprises physical components incorporating different elements and the workplace environment and structure. In contrast, the psychosocial variables incorporate working conditions, job congruity, and social help.

The study's third indicator of independent variable work values is *work interactions*. Bongco and Ancho (2019) stated that teaching is about relationships that lead to *work interactions*. While students, guardians, and administrators anticipate joining forces with teachers, *work interactions* with colleagues will assume the biggest job of making the most of the work and developing as an expert. That is the reason it's so basic to be a good

colleague. Not exclusively will it advantage the work; however, it likewise will set a solid guide to the students. In the present fierce TV and Internet culture, kids need to see the grown-ups communicating collegiality, mindful and concern in reality. *Work interactions* with colleagues are a significant activity property for some workers. To draw in and hold workers, supervisors along these lines need to consider how to make and safeguard top-notch work interactions (Dur, 2009). In addition, an individual in solitude will have a hard time getting along with the working surrounding. One should be an excellent decent collaborator to make his mark at the workplace. He needs to interact with his co-workers and offer plans to reach better arrangements. Workers must work as one for quicker and powerful outcomes. Keeping up solid relationships with fellow workers is fundamental as an individual invests his most incredible energy at the workplace.

Work activities are the fourth indicator of the independent variable work values. *Work activities* are best tuned in when it permits innovativeness, sharing thoughts, aptitudes, and abilities, and getting imaginative plans to create results. They are also best slanted towards logical sorts of exercises that connect with them to look for new data and arrangements-comprehending what the employees want to take part as far as work exercises are fundamental because individuals become most imaginative and persuaded when they are interested, fulfilled, and challenged by the work itself (Estimo & Aguilar, 2017). Additionally, authoritative innovativeness starts when individuals love doing, like *work activities*. The employees of educational institutions will, even more, be glad and profitable if the work activities doled out to them would suit their capacities and abilities just as their inclinations. It is in a perfect world important that what is given in the workplace must address those that the employees want to perform besides their essential capacities as educators and office staff.

Overall, an individual's work values may significantly impact their professional decision. *Work values* are beliefs or principles related to your profession or place of employment. They describe what you believe is important in your professional life. Work values relate to your interests, goals, and preferred career path. It's critical to think about these principles as you assess your present job satisfaction and contemplate your future career options. In the end, people are happy when their values and work are aligned. In fact, how your values connect with your work environment determines job happiness more than any other component. As a result, it's critical to assess your job values to choose your priorities.

Work Engagement

As an independent variable, work engagement is a positive, satisfying, work-related perspective portrayed by vigor, dedication, and absorption. Instead of a flitting and explicit state, engagement alludes to a progressively persevering and unavoidable full feeling of subjective expression that is not centered on a specific article, occasion, individual, or conduct. Vigor is described by elevated vitality levels and mental versatility while working, the ability to put exertion in one's work, and tirelessness even notwithstanding challenges. Dedication alludes to being firmly associated with one's work and encountering a feeling of criticalness, energy, motivation, pride, and challenge. Absorption is described by being completely focused and cheerfully engaged in one's work, whereby time passes rapidly. One experiences issues with disconnecting oneself from work (Boikanyo & Heyns, 2019).

This way, work engagement is a significant marker among work frames of mind. The data identified with work learning, work assets, work execution, turnover aim, advancement, and administration manner can be procured to mirror a person's eagerness to be dedicated to its activity (Song, Kolb, Lee, & Kim, 2012). When the work engagement is at a lower level, an individual will generally distance from the activity job to keep the self from producing the exhibition required for the activity job.

Moreover, work engagement interceded the connection between employment assets and turnover aim; the more creative the job, the larger amounts of engagement is decidedly identified with work-related approaches, for example, work fulfilment, work involvement, and organizational commitment, it, however, seems to be a distinct concept and the more emphatically identified with occupation performance (Berg, Wrzesniewski, & Dutton, 2010).

In addition, institutions expect personnel to be proactive, show activity, and stay focused on performing only requirements (Purcell, 2014). Institutional agility requires workers who show vitality and self-assurance

and exhibit veritable eagerness and energy for their work (Bakker & Schaufeli, 2014). To summarize, present institutions need a connection with work power.

Further, engaged employees need to contribute, have a feeling of having a place, protect the association, try sincerely, and are not keen on moving to different employers. Workers who are not engaged cause a gap between employees' exertion and institutional effectiveness. This essentially influences an association's financial performance (Saks, 2017).

Subsequently, worker engagement is a state of an employee who feels included, submitted, energetic, and enabled and shows those emotions in work conduct as characterized by Mone and London (2018). It is in this manner the degree of responsibility and inclusion a worker has towards their association and its qualities. The association must create and sustain engagement, which requires a two-route connection between employer and worker. Along these lines, work engagement is a gauge that decides an individual's relationship with the institution (Patro, 2013).

Work engagement is a work environment approach bringing about the right conditions for all institution personnel to give their best every day, focused on their institution's objectives and qualities, inspired to add to hierarchical achievement, with their upgraded feeling prosperity. Work engagement depends on trust, uprightness, two-way responsibility, and correspondence between an association and its individuals. It is an approach that expands the odds of achievement, adding to institutional and individual performance, efficiency, and prosperity. It tends to be estimated. It fluctuates from poor to extraordinary. It very well may be supported and drastically expanded; it tends to be lost and discarded (McLeod, 2012).

The first indicator of work engagement is *vigor*. *Vigor* is a substantial approach to consider engagement. On the off chance that your employees seem enthusiastic, fiery, and intrigued by the work they do, they are likely locked in. If it doesn't depict your employees, you could unquestionably search for new ones, yet prescribe beginning with joining forces with them persistently improve the work that they do (Little, 2017). *Vigor* is the eagerness that can be felt from the significant level of vitality and continuance of the psyche while working, the readiness to give the best in a vocation, and diligence when confronting an issue (Schaufeli, 2017).

The second indicator of the independent variable, work engagement, is *dedication*. *Dedication* is thinking about something to an outrageous degree. When you are devoted, you give all you have the majority of your endeavors—to a reason or an undertaking. This is a significant quality to represent in the work environment specifically (Kudisch, 2017). Furthermore, whenever an employee demonstrates that he needs to study his activity, it indicates dedication in the work environment. Needing to develop and find out about a position accentuates that a worker thinks about self-improvement and the organization's prosperity. Stagnation is going to influence an organization's main concern. Approaches to demonstrating development in an occupation position are posing inquiries, taking classes for further improvement, and remaining inspired by new advancements in the organization's field (Scott, 2018).

The third indicator of the dependent variable, work engagement, is *absorption*. *Work absorption* is one of the three qualities or signs of work engagement, the others being vigor and dedication. Employees completely absorbed by their work are what each employer needs (Gaither, 2016). In addition, if your work absorbs you, you are finished overwhelmed by what you do. You cherish what you do. You can hardly wait to do what you do. You are always and gladly telling other individuals, "Take a look at what I get the chance to do!" You show the world who you are by what you do because an enormous piece of what you do is who you are.

Generally, work engagement refers to employees' relationship with their work; however, employee engagement may also include the relationship with the association. The emotional commitment the employee has to the organization and its goals. They don't work just for remuneration or the next promotion but work on behalf of the organization's goals. When employees care, when they are engaged, they use flexible effort. Employee engagement in work is about being included fully as a team member, focused on clear goals, trusted and empowered, receiving regular and constructive feedback, developing new skills, and being thanked and recognized for achievement.

Personal Effectiveness

Personal effectiveness alludes to utilizing your time and utilizing the assets available to you to perform as well as expected in your working environment. This will, at that point, mean you will be brilliant in accomplishing your objectives (Kornelius, 2018) and help review existing approaches and practices with an expectation that they can upgrade work performance and employment effectiveness among teachers (Usop, Askander, Langguyuan-Kadtong, & Usop, 2013).

This way, personal effectiveness is the capacity to positively and positively affect others by passing on thoughts and data plainly and powerfully, as Chaudhary and Singh (2017) stated. It includes arranging and organizing accessible methods by utilizing relational abilities to help assemble effective working relationships with others and diminish individual pressure. Individual adequacy adds to the general viability of an individual both in social and expert life. Individual personal effectiveness of an individual is reliant on their comprehension of themselves as well as other people.

On the other hand, according to a corporate coach group, personal effectiveness signifies a proportion of your proficiency, which means your capacity to make the most significant incentive in the base time and exertion; and gain great ground even with troubles. Personal effectiveness alludes to utilizing all the individual assets available to you, abilities, aptitudes, vitality, and time to empower you to accomplish work and life objectives (Juneja & Malhotra, 2015).

Furthermore, personal effectiveness matches with the way of thinking of constant improvement, persistently working after upgrading the current aptitudes and capacities still as cited by Juneja and Malhotra (2015). In addition, individual viability includes objective setting, individual improvement, activity, positive self-talk, time the board, stress the board, mindfulness, and evaluation, assuming the liability of one's work and making greatness and progress. This way, personal effectiveness could be better comprehended by its three primary parts or indicators: Self-disclosure, which means sharing of thoughts, feeling, feelings, encounters with others; Openness to feedback which means giving, getting, and tolerating criticism from others; and perceptiveness which means being progressively mindful about the conduct, sentiments, and feelings of other individuals. In this way, personal effectiveness implies the capacity, capability, abilities, information, assets, and so forth to amplify and realize one's maximum capacity and achieve objectives and goals.

The first indicator of the dependent variable personal effectiveness is *self-disclosure*. *Self-disclosure* is uncovering how you're responding to the present work demands and giving essential data from an earlier time. These are frequently things that could never have been talked about. It settles on for better authoritative understanding and choices in business, and it frequently emphatically impacts self-awareness and one's professional alternatives. Self-disclosure is both conventional and one of a kind (Erwin, 2011). Consequently, *self-disclosure* is a significant administration attribute since it relates straightforwardly to trust. The more open individuals appear, the more prominent they are trusted (Stoner, 2016). Further, *self-disclosure* entails more than how much you are willing to tell others about yourself; it is also a crucial building block of intimacy and vital to a wide variety of social relationships (Kendra, 2019).

The second indicator of the dependent variable personal effectiveness is *openness to feedback*. *Openness to feedback* is essential in working environments: working environments need compelling correspondence to succeed and flourish. Just as expanding staff confidence, feedback causes us to become familiar with ourselves, our qualities and shortcomings, our practices, and how our activities influence others. It additionally builds our mindfulness and empowers self-awareness (Collier, 2019). *Openness to feedback* on how you're going at work makes a fundamental commitment to your advancement as a professional since it gives bits of knowledge into how others experience you and your work. Utilized wisely, what you gain from feedback can improve working connections, increment profitability, and empower change (Fitzell, 2015). Furthermore, while most professionals appreciate a gesture of congratulations for occupation very much done, many find critical feedback challenging to take, mainly if they judge it out of line or unjustified. Critical feedback, anyway valuable the purpose, is then experienced as undermining, which can prompt individuals to become guarded, obstructing the learning potential.

The third indicator of the dependent variable personal effectiveness is *perceptiveness*. *Perceptiveness* is good at getting things or making sense of things. Perceptive individuals are clever, shrewd, and ready to perceive what others can't. They imagine the potential outcomes, grasping what could be instead of being happy with the status quo of what is. While some appear to have this ability inherently, others can utilize their delicate aptitudes to assist them with turning out to be increasingly perceptive like the leaders they respect (Blaschka, 2019). Furthermore, perceptiveness is a key attribute of the creative mind. It empowers us to decipher thoughts diversely from other people, understanding new viewpoints and potential outcomes. It may be seen how we alluded to the creative mind instead of sight or hearing (or any of different faculties, so far as that is concerned). Perception is an activity completed by the mind (Picasso, 2019).

Generally speaking, personal effectiveness at work entails giving your best effort. When you use personal effectiveness in the workplace, you will manage your time effectively, stay on track, meet deadlines, and complete all of your tasks to the best of your abilities. It is to build and transmit a sense of direction to preserve and improve one's own self-esteem and adjust one's approach or style to various people and situations. Working effectively under pressure demonstrates resilience in dealing with challenges and understanding one's own strengths and flaws. It also takes responsibility for one's own learning and development needs by seeking feedback on performance and taking positive steps to improve. Clarifying the working process and the content requires the willingness to make decisions and accept responsibility for dealing with setbacks and disappointments. Setting and maintaining high standards is a key component of personal effectiveness.

Correlation Between Measures

School culture and teacher direction are essential in deciding a school's excellence. Several studies have been conducted to look at school culture with teacher focus and personal effectiveness. However, the studies on analyzing the connection between these two components are deficient. Researchers frequently center. In addition, Uha (2010) likewise exhibited that culture improves human resource conduct and inspiration, prompting its presentation and fulfilment of authoritative objectives. Concerning the above perspectives, school culture has an immediate positive association with personal effectiveness. This foresees that positive and solid school culture can cause a regular staff to perform and accomplish destinations. In contrast, a negative and frail culture may demotivate an exceptional staff to fail to meet expectations and end up with no accomplishment.

Many hypothetical and exact confirmations argue that culture matters in all open and private associations. Further, Darmawan (2013) assumed that the school culture of an institution is connected to its prosperity as it rouses workers to accomplish classified goals and is associated with personal effectiveness. He further focused that the board should focus on its commanding culture for an institution to create and continue the upper hand over opponents. Reliably, the way of life in instructive establishments stimulates energy in staff to achieve instructive objectives.

Additionally, some studies showed that the school's culture impacts teachers' effectiveness. Sawchuck (2011) revealed that positive and dominant school culture can nourish teachers' leadership traits and effectiveness. Also, in their study, Sheppard, Hurley, and Dibbon (2010) stated that teachers tended to improve morale and motivation through a school culture that encourages the development of teacher effectiveness. The study of Kabler (2013) found that school culture has a significant relationship with teacher effectiveness. Any kind of reformation is impossible or hard to be done if the existing culture is not in line with the reformation that is to be carried out. In addition, teachers' beliefs, values, attitudes, and assumptions, supporting staff, and school leaders should align with the reformations. If the school community's culture is positive towards the reformation, thus the goal also seems to be positive. In other words, school culture is shaped by its community, and teacher effectiveness has a strong influence in determining school achievement (Fiske, 2010).

Moreover, work values are typically connected with how employees do their work which might be principled and progress personal effectiveness. Belyn (2020) stated that people with a decent work value are typically exceptionally beneficial individuals who work quicker than impact personal effectiveness. They routinely achieve more work, more rapidly than the individuals who lack work values, for they don't stop until the work entrusted with is finished. In any event, to a limited extent, this is additionally because of the personal

effectiveness way that they wish to seem, by all accounts, to be stronger employees. In this manner, they wish to give off an impression of being of more advantage to their supervisors and the organization. Essentially, work values can allude to how you feel about your activity or profession, so it covers your frame of mind and conduct, giving you high personal effectiveness. It likewise relates to how you carry out your responsibility or the obligations that come appended with it (Luenendock, 2020). It is essential to have a decent and solid hard work value to link with personal effectiveness. Eventually, it will demonstrate the quality of your character and present you as an inside and out constructive individual.

Employees' work engagement to their institutions exceptionally influences their performance as personal effectiveness. It is the extent to which the worker is engaged with their work and is faithful to their institution (Ajibade & Ayinla, 2014). Executives worldwide state that improving work engagement is one of their main five worldwide business methodologies. In addition to the fact that work engagement can fundamentally influence representative profitability, it is likewise a link to personal effectiveness. There is a close relationship between personal effectiveness and work engagement. Gallup Organization studied this relationship in America and discovered employees who are integrated with work are faithful for association and enthusiastic and ready to do tasks. Employees integrated with work engagement give everything for organizations goals, demonstrate better performance, help for organizations achievement, and take responsibilities. This prompts employees' effectiveness in the organization (San & Tok, 2017).

As supported by Kanesan, Ling, and Hassan's (2018) study, the value of teachers' work and school culture affects school performance and students' ability. It leads to a connection between work values and school culture. Henceforth, teachers must train optimistic behavior and work an incentive towards advancement. Even though components of economic well-being, activity, and pay are poor indicators of job effectiveness, these dimensions should be tended to by school pioneers to guarantee the institution's smooth running. On the off chance that this dimension isn't a necessary piece of significant worth administration, it will surely cause conflict inside the organization.

All in all, the related studies featured in the previous paragraphs present a chance to improve the comprehension of the contexts and reasonable results of the varied disappointment and achievement factors, just as to distinguish connection between the independent variables- school culture, work values, work engagement and dependent variable- personal effectiveness. The different concepts that portray a relationship with the culture and work suggest linkages that hypothesize how it affects personally by the teachers. It gives a system to evaluate the organization and environment, which is the school, that are keys to fruitful personal effectiveness. Furthermore, these ideas displayed in the related writing show how factors connected causally to accomplish ideal benchmark for private school teachers.

Theoretical Framework

The study was anchored on Johari Window's Theory formulated by Luft and Ingham (1955) to outline and develop self-awareness and mutual understanding between individuals within a group, leading to personal effectiveness. Further, the theory turned out to be a broadly utilized model for understanding and training self-awareness, personal development, improving communications, interpersonal relationships, group dynamics, team development, and inter-group relationships associated with school culture, work values, and work engagement.

It was affixed to three propositions: the link between school culture and personal effectiveness. School culture improves teachers' conduct and inspiration, prompting its presentation and authoritative objectives (Uha, 2010). The culture of the school has an immediate association with personal effectiveness. Positive and solid school culture can cause teachers to perform and accomplish destinations like this foreseen. In contrast, a negative and frail culture may demotivate an exceptional teacher to fail to meet expectations and end up with no accomplishment.

Second, the link between work values and personal effectiveness revealed that work values could allude to how you feel about your activity or profession, covering your frame of mind and conduct. It likewise relates to how you carry out your responsibility or the obligations that come appended with it (Luenendock, 2017). It is

essential to have decent and solid complex work values to link with personal effectiveness. Eventually, it will demonstrate the quality of your character and present you as an inside and out constructive individual.

Third, the link between work engagement and personal effectiveness was supported by Ajibade and Ayinla (2014), which cite that employees' work engagement to their institutions exceptionally influences their performance just as personal effectiveness. It is the extent to which the worker is engaged with their work and is faithful to their institution.

Conceptual framework

This conceptual framework represents the researcher's writing synthesis on the most proficient method to clarify a phenomenon. It maps out the actions required throughout the study, given past information of other researchers' perspectives and perceptions regarding research (Regoniel, 2015). In other words, this framework is the researcher's comprehension of how the particular variables in the study associate with one another. Hence, it recognizes the variables required in the research. It is the researcher's "map" in seeking after the study.

The hypothesized model was made up of two latent variables: exogenous and endogenous variables of the study. The exogenous factors of the study were *school culture*, *work values*, and *work engagement*. At the same time, the endogenous variable was *personal effectiveness*. Since latent variables are not observed directly, it pursues that they can't be observed directly. This construct is related to multiple measured, observed variables. Along these lines, the extent of the regression paths from the latent variable to the observed variables is one of the vital interests of the study.

RESEARCH METHOD

The study used a quantitative research method, descriptive and structural equation modelling. Quantitative methods highlighted objective measurements and the statistical or numerical interpretation of data gathered through questionnaires and surveys or by controlling previous statistical data utilizing statistical methods. Quantitative research focuses on gathering numerical information and making conclusions across people or explaining a particular phenomenon. First, the study applied descriptive research intended to portray the members authentically. Moreover, descriptive research was tied in with describing people who were part of the study. On the contrary, causal research falls under detailed research due to its effect relationship between two variables (Babbie, 2010). Second, the study used a structural equation model. In contrast with other statistical methods, structural equation modelling was a more complicated method of data analysis. It indicated a structure for the covariance between observed variables. Subsequently, it offers increasingly generous and increasingly substantial outcomes (Hulin, Netemeyer, & Cudeck, 2001). Inference on the data was more prominent, and explaining the outcomes was more complex than other data interpretation methods. The structural equation model speaks to the hypothesis that shows constructs were identified with different constructs. Structural equation modelling, also called causal modeling because it tests the proposed casual relationships (Hancock, 2019). Moreover, seemingly, structural equation modeling is one of the most well-known statistical methodologies accessible to quantitative researchers (Kaplan, 2010).

The researcher conducted the study in private schools of Davao City, Region XI, This was being considered as the area for the study since the researcher would want to discover in a more extensive degree whether school culture, work values, and work engagement correlate with personal effectiveness in private schools. The respondents of this study were teachers from different private schools of the Basic Education Department in region XI. They were the best ones for responding to the study. They can provide useful information for testing the study's hypothesis. The survey questions were in electronic Google form since it was affected by the Pandemic Corona Virus 19. The researcher identified the number of basic education private school teachers. A stratified random sampling technique was used in selecting the respondents. Following the rule of the number of respondents appropriate for structural equation modeling (Yuan, Wu, & Bentler, 2011) is between 300 to 400. Barred in the study were the school administrators/directors, principals, academic coordinators of the basic education private schools, and the individuals who were rejected in noting the survey questionnaire. The respondents can be pulled back from the study on the off chance that they submit distortion,

plagiarism, and other moral offenses or the respondents were not feeling well and had special needs. Further, they were allowed to pull back from participating in the conduct of the study on the off chance that they felt awkward in answering the survey. The researcher respected their decision with regards to answering the said survey questionnaire. Additionally, to ensure that there was no violation of ethical rules of conduct associated with the administration of this research, several precautions were taken into consideration. Primarily, it will be the approval and strict adherence to the rules and guidelines of the university established. All necessary written approval was granted to the researcher before any part of the survey administration was conducted.

The data gathered in this study were used to compute hypotheses at alpha 0.05 level of significance with the following statistical tools: mean was used to measure the level between school culture, work values, work engagement, and personal effectiveness of the Basic Education private school teachers; pearson product moment correlation was used to determine the relationships between school culture, work values, work engagement, and personal effectiveness; multiple regression analysis was employed to estimate the strength of the relationship between school culture, work values, work engagement, and personal effectiveness, and the independent variables' predictive power to the dependent variable and; structural equation modeling was used to explore the best fit model. There will be a need to conduct a factor analysis on the latent variables in testing the factors. Yuan, Wu, and Bentler (2010) suggested a cut-off of 0.50 in modeling construction safety culture. According to Barrett (2007), the essence of the test is to ensure the elimination of attributes with low correlations with the attributes of other latent factors in the final model. The cut-off value is affected by sample size, but a range of 0.45 and 0.50 is deemed appropriate.

In evaluating the goodness of fit in the models, the following indices were computed: CMIN/DF, Tucker-Lewis Index (TLI), Comparative Fit Index (CFI), and Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA) and P of close fit.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Presented in Table 1 is the level of a school culture which is measured by professional collaboration, affiliative collegiality, and self-determination/efficacy. It recorded an overall mean rating of 4.05, described as *high*. This indicated that basic education private school teachers often manifest school culture. Indicators used under school culture were a *professional collaboration* with 4.02, *affiliative collegiality* with 4.08, and *self-determination/efficacy* with 4.04. The three indicators were labeled as *high*.

Table 1. Level of School Culture

Items	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Professional Collaboration	0.62	4.02	High
Affiliative Collegiality	0.53	4.08	High
Self-determination/Efficacy	0.54	4.04	High
Overall	0.51	4.05	High

The high level of *school culture* was high due to the ratings given by teachers on professional collaboration, affiliative collegiality, and self-determination/efficacy. These were manifested by teachers that discuss instructional strategies and curriculum issues, work together to develop the school schedule, and collaborate to develop the student behavior code. The high result on school culture as viewed by teachers is congruent to the ideas of Trepatharan and Tayiam (2014), Stearns, Banerjee, Mickelson, and Moller (2014), and Fisher, Frey, and Pumpian (2012) that school culture has been demonstrated to be a moderately solid and consistently, reliably perceptive factor among the numerous elements influencing the degree to which educators are content with their jobs. It might be that school culture influences school effectiveness legitimately, additionally utilizing the impact of teachers' work fulfillment. Also, through showing practices, school hierarchical culture can likewise affect student results. Further, positive school culture empowers more prominent exertion and efficiency, improves joint collegial effort, underpins fruitful change and improvement endeavors, fabricates duty and distinguishing proof of students and teachers with your school, and intensifies vitality and inspiration

of staff individuals and students. Furthermore, schools should be fostering environments for professional collaboration, work values, and self-determination for both staff and children. People must treat and value one another, share their teaching ideas and encourage one another in today's classrooms. The cornerstone for healthy school culture and optimizing student learning is relationship vitality with students, parents, the community, and, most importantly, with one another (Wagner, 2006).

Presented in Table 2 is the level of work values measured in terms of core values, work environments, work interactions, and work activities. It registered an overall mean rating of 4.03, which is described as *High*. This means that basic education private school teachers' work values were often manifested. Individually, *work interactions* registered the highest mean rating of 4.12, followed by *core values* with 4.06, then *work environment* with 3.99, and the lowest mean rating of 3.96 was obtained by *work activities*. All indicators garnered *high* ratings.

Table 2. Level of Work Values

Items	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Core Values	0.44	4.06	High
Work Environment	0.46	3.99	High
Work Interactions	0.48	4.12	High
Work Activities	0.47	3.96	High
Overall	0.38	4.03	High

The high level of *work values* is attributed to teachers' core values, work environment, work interactions, and work activities. This is evident when teachers meet their goals, believe in their core beliefs, care and trust themselves and others, and tell the truth and know that others are telling the truth. The manifestations have been instilled in every teacher, which aligned to the views of several authors (McKay, 2018; Hénard & Roseveare, 2012; Park & Hill, 2016; Meriac, Woehr, Gorman, & Thomas, 2013) that work values incorporate things like trustworthiness, administration, sense of pride, regard for other people, harmony, and achievement. Also, positive work values produce results from the learners that continue the work progress and mental improvement of the students through quality instructing in higher education which truly matters for student learning results. Additionally, employers value working admirably and look for workers with solid, hard-working values. Work values can be characterized as many attributes and practices that mirror an individual's convictions, qualities, dispositions, and practices toward work.

Presented in Table 3 is the level of work engagement measured in terms of vigor, dedication, and absorption. The overall mean recorded was 4.02 or *high*. This means that basic education private school teachers' work engagement was often manifested. Specifically, the level of work engagement in terms of *dedication* garnered the highest mean rating of 4.19, which is described as *high*. In addition, *vigor* got a mean rating of 3.94, which is labeled as *high*. On the other hand, *absorption* recorded the lowest mean rating of 3.93 or *high*.

Table 3. Level of Work Engagement

Items	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Vigor	0.50	3.94	High
Dedication	0.55	4.19	High
Absorption	0.53	3.93	High
Overall	0.45	4.02	High

The level of *work engagement* was high due to the high ratings given by teachers on vigor, dedication, and absorption. This was demonstrated by teachers stating that they are proud of their work, claiming that their job is challenging, and time flies when they are working. These manifestations are evident in the claims of several authors like Purcell (2014), Bakker and Schaufeli (2014), and Saks (2017) that personnel must be proactive, show activity and stay focused on performing at exclusive requirements. It requires workers to show

vitality and self-assurance and exhibit veritable eagerness and energy for their work. Also, engaged employees need to contribute, have a feeling of having a place, protect the association, try sincerely, and are not keen on moving to different employers. Workers who are not engaged cause a gap between employees' exertion and institutional effectiveness. This essentially influences an association's financial performance.

Presented in Table 4 is the level of personal effectiveness of basic education private school teachers in Region XI, which is measured in terms of self-disclosure, openness to feedback, and perceptiveness. It garnered an overall mean rating of 3.69, labeled as *high*, which means that private school teachers often manifested personal effectiveness. The domain *openness to feedback* got the highest mean rating of 3.77 or *high*, followed by the other domains with corresponding mean scores as arranged from highest to lowest, namely, *self-disclosure* with 3.75 and *perceptiveness* with 3.56 or *high*.

Table 4. Level of Personal Effectiveness

Items	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Self-disclosure	0.50	3.75	High
Openness to Feedback	0.52	3.77	High
Perceptiveness	0.64	3.56	High
Overall	0.46	3.69	High

The level of *personal effectiveness* was high due to teachers' high ratings on self-disclosure, openness to feedback, and perceptiveness. Indeed, teachers demonstrated it by (items in table 2 with mean of 4.14, 4.08 and Table 1 with mean of 4.11). This manifestation was following the views of different authors that Kornelius (2018), Chaudhary and Singh (2017), and Osborn (2019) that personal effectiveness alludes to utilizing your time and utilizing the assets available to you to perform as well as could be expected in your working environment. This will, at that point, mean you will be brilliant in accomplishing your objectives. Also, it pointed out the capacity to positively affect others by passing on thoughts and data plainly and powerfully. Additionally, the shared objective in the working environment must arrive at their maximum capacity both in their vocation and throughout everyday life. Likewise, personal effectiveness can be better understood by looking at its three main components or indicators: self-disclosure, which entails sharing one's thoughts, feelings, and experiences with others; openness to feedback, which entails giving, receiving, and tolerating criticism from others; and perceptiveness, which entails becoming increasingly aware of other people's actions, sentiments, and feelings. Personal effectiveness, in this sense, refers to the capacity, capability, abilities, information, and assets, among other things, to amplify and actualize one's full potential and achieve objectives and goals (Juneja & Malhotra, 2018)

Table 5.1 shows the relationship between the school culture and personal effectiveness of basic education private schools in Region XI. It can be gleaned on the table that there was a significant relationship between school culture and personal effectiveness with an overall correlation coefficient of 0.200, which is significant at a 0.05 level of significance. It could be stated that there is a significant relationship between school culture and the personal effectiveness of private school teachers. Specifically, when the indicators of school culture are correlated with personal effectiveness, all the indicators were found to be significant at a 0.05 level of significance, with *professional collaboration* having a correlation coefficient of 0.149, *affiliative collegiality* with 0.177, and *self-determination/efficacy* with 0.218.

Table 5.1. Significance of the Relationship between School Culture and Personal Effectiveness

School Culture	Personal Effectiveness			
	Self-Disclosure	Openness to Feedback	Perceptiveness	Overall
Professional Collaboration	.150**	.183**	.054	.149**
	.002	.000	.266	.002

Affiliative Collegiality	.164** .001	.250** .000	.048	.177**
Self-determination/Efficacy	.245** .000	.248** .000	.074	.218**
			.128	.000
Overall	.206** .000	.249** .000	.065	.200**
			.179	.000

The result follows the findings of Sawchuck (2011), which revealed a positive and dominant school culture could nourish the personal effectiveness among teachers. Also, Sheppard, Hurley, and Dibbon (2010) stated that teachers tended to improve morale and motivation through a school culture that encourages the development of teacher effectiveness. Similarly, Kabler (2013) found that school culture has a significant relationship with teacher effectiveness. Any kind of reformation is impossible or hard to be done if the existing culture is not in line with the reformation that is to be carried out. In addition, teachers' beliefs, values, attitudes, and assumptions, supporting staff and school leadership should be in line with the reformations that to be made.

Table 5.2 showed the relationship between work values and personal effectiveness of basic education private school teachers in Region XI. It was found that there was a significant relationship between work values and personal effectiveness with an overall correlation coefficient of 0.304, which is significant at 0.05 in the level of significance. Further, this indicates that work values and personal effects were significantly correlated. Additionally, when the indicators of work values were correlated to personal effectiveness, three indicators were significantly correlated at 0.05 level of significance where *core values* had a correlation coefficient of 0.166, *work environments* with 0.35, and *work activities* with 0.394.

Table 5.2. Significance of the Relationship between Work Values and Personal Effectiveness

Work Values	Personal Effectiveness			
	Self-Disclosure	Openness to Feedback	Perceptiveness	Overall
Core Values	.210** .000	.237** .000	-.002 .964	.166** .001
Work Environments	.384** .000	.344** .000	.173** .000	.350** .000
Work Interactions	.161** .001	.163** .001	-.066 .171	.089 .064
Work Activities	.372** .000	.408** .000	.222** .000	.394** .000
Overall	.343** .000	.351** .000	.100*	.304** .000

There is a significant relationship between teachers' work values and personal effectiveness. The result supports Belyn's (2020) idea that work values are typically connected with how employees do their work, which might be seen as principled and will progress personal effectiveness. People with decent work values are typically exceptionally beneficial individuals who work quicker, impacting personal effectiveness. They routinely achieve more work, more rapidly than the individuals who lack work values, for they don't stop until the work entrusted with is finished. In any event, to a limited extent, this is additionally because of the personal effectiveness way that they wish to seem, by all accounts, to be stronger employees. In this manner, they wish to give off an impression of being of more advantage to their supervisors and the organization. Additionally, Luenendock (2020) indicated that work values could allude to an individual how they feel about their activity or profession, so it covers their frame of mind and conduct, which will give them high personal effectiveness.

Presented in Table 5.3 is the significance of the relationship between work engagement and personal effectiveness of basic education private school teachers in Region XI. It registered an overall correlation coefficient of 0.346, which is significant at 0.05 in the significance level. This means that work engagement is significantly correlated with personal effectiveness.

The data shows that the three domains of work engagement have a probability value of 0.000 towards teachers' effectiveness. It can be observed that *absorption* got the highest correlation towards teachers' effectiveness with 0.41, the *vigor* with 0.386, and *dedication* with 0.095.

Table 5.3. Significance of the Relationship between Work Engagement and Personal Effectiveness

Work Engagement	Personal Effectiveness			
	Self-Disclosure	Openness to Feedback	Perceptiveness	Overall
Vigor	.366** .000	.384** .000	.230** .000	.386** .000
Dedication	.103** .032	.210** .000	-.047 .331	.095* .048
Absorption	.400** .000	.357** .000	.276** .000	.410** .000
Overall	.337** .000	.371** .000	.176 .000	.346** .000

There is a significant relationship between work engagement and the personal effectiveness of teachers. The term engagement has been defined in many different ways. Work engagement is defined as a positive, gratifying, affective- motivational state of work-related happiness. Despite its popularity, there is a lack of empirical work engagement research in the academe. Given our field's focus on performance development, the relationship between work engagement and performance to personal effectiveness deserves special study (Kolb & Kim 2013). Employees' commitment to their organizations has a significant impact on their performance and personal effectiveness. It is the degree to which workers are invested in their work and loyal to their employer (Ajibade & Ayinla, 2014). According to executives, improving work engagement is one of the top five global approaches. Work engagement links to personal effectiveness and significantly impacts representative profitability. Furthermore, Darolia, Darolia, and Kumari (2010) indicated that people could feel committed to an association, top management, administrators, or a specific work gathering. Work engagement has been examined concerning the profession, union, and profession Studies demonstrating occurrences of high work engagement have likewise shown to identify with influential execution related to personal effectiveness profoundly.

Table 6 displayed the influence of school culture, work values, and work engagement on the personal effectiveness of private school teachers. The analysis shows that the standard coefficient of work engagement has the highest beta of 0.269. It indicates that work engagement has a greater influence on teachers' personal effectiveness than work values with 0.151. Moreover, as indicated by the F-value of 21.327 with a corresponding p-value of 0.000, the regression model is therefore significant. Hence, it leads to the rejection of the null hypothesis. It could be stated that there is a variable that can predict the personal effectiveness of basic education private school teachers in Region XI.

Table 6. Significance on the Influence of School Culture, Work Values, and Work Engagement on the Personal Effectiveness

	Personal Effectiveness			
	B	β	t	Sig.
Constant	1.996		8.686	.000
School Culture	-.036	-.040	-.688	.492
Work Values	.183	.151	2.351	.019
Work Engagement	.275	.269	4.285	.000
R	.362			
R ²	.131			
ΔR	.125			
F	21.327			
ρ	.000			

In addition, the R² of 0.134 signifies that 13.4 percent of the variation in personal effectiveness is explained by the predictor variables work engagement and work values. This would mean that 86.6 percent of the variation can be attributed to other factors aside from these three variables.

The singular capacities of the independent variables showed that work values and work engagement significantly influence the dependent variable. The three independent variables need each other to significantly influence the dependent variable. The result can be supported by the findings of San and Tok (2017) that employees who are integrated with work are faithful to the association and enthusiastic and ready to do tasks. Additionally, Gostick and Elton (2011) say employees who are integrated with work engagement give everything for organizations goals, demonstrate better performance, help for organizations achievement, and take responsibilities. This prompts the effectiveness of employees in the organization.

Best Fit Model

As presented in the table below, it can be observed that among the three latent exogenous variables, work values have the highest beta, equal to .802. School culture has the weakest beta of -.342. This means that work values have the highest influence on latent personal effectiveness while school culture also brings an inverse impact on personal effectiveness.

Direct and Indirect Effects of the Independent Variables on Personal Effectiveness of Best Fit Model

Variables	Direct Effect	Indirect Effect	Total Effect
School Culture	-.342	-	-.342
Work Values	.802	-	.802
Work Engagement	-	-	-

Evaluation of the fit on the data of best fit model is presented in Table 20. As reflected in the table, the model shows the best fit compared to the previous models. The fit indices passed the accepted values like a CMIN/DF of 1.462 with a p-value of 0.064, RMSEA of 0.033, NFI = 0.982, TLI = 0.989, CFI = 0.994, and GFI = 0.983 which signifies model fit. This means that this is the best model to explain personal effectiveness.

Table 20
The goodness of Fit Measures of Structural Best Fit Model

INDEX	CRITERION	MODEL FIT VALUE
P-Close	> 0.05	.064
CMIN/DF	0 < value < 2	1.462
GFI	> 0.95	.983
CFI	> 0.95	.994
NFI	> 0.95	.982
TLI	> 0.95	.989
RMSEA	< 0.05	.033

Legend:

CMIN/DF	-	Chi-Square/Degrees of Freedom
NFI	-	Normed Fit Index
TLI	-	Tucker-Lewis Index
CFI	-	Comparative Fit Index
GFI	-	Goodness of Fit Index
RMSEA	-	Root Means Square of Error Approximation
P-close	-	P of Close Fit

Table 21 presents the regression weights exhibited by the influence between latent variables and between measured and latent variables. Among the paths presented in this model, paths between latent

variables WORK VALUES and PERSONAL_EFFECTIVENESS and SCHOOL CULTURE, and PERSONAL_EFFECTIVENESS obtained p-values that are less than .01. This indicates that work values and school culture significantly explained personal effectiveness.

Table 21

Estimates of Variable Regression Weights in Generated Best Fit Model

			Estimate	S.E.	Beta	C.R.	P-value
PERSONAL_EFFECTIVENESS	<	WORK VALUES	1.251	.196	.802	6.380	***
WORK ENGAGEMENT	<	WORK VALUES	1.022	.153	.848	6.663	***
WORK ENGAGEMENT	<	SCHOOL CULTURE	.031	.102	.032	.299	.765
PERSONAL_EFFECTIVENESS	<	SCHOOL CULTURE	-.421	.137	-.342	-3.069	.002
PC	<	SCHOOL CULTURE	1.000		.683		
AC	<	SCHOOL CULTURE	1.045	.079	.832	13.180	***
SD	<	SCHOOL CULTURE	1.151	.085	.895	13.510	***
WA	<	WORK VALUES	1.000		.712		
WE	<	WORK VALUES	.896	.067	.654	13.449	***
AN	<	WORK ENGAGEMENT	1.000		.752		
VR	<	WORK ENGAGEMENT	1.028	.070	.832	14.723	***
SE	<	PERSONAL_EFFECTIVENESS	1.000		1.043		
OF	<	PERSONAL_EFFECTIVENESS	.989	.076	.988	12.937	***
PS	<	PERSONAL_EFFECTIVENESS	.649	.116	.529	5.618	***

Legend:

PC- Professional Collaboration

AC- Affiliative Collegiality

SD- Self-determination

CV- Core Values

WE- Work Environment

WI- Work Interactions

WA- Work Activities

VR- Vigor

DN- Dedication

AN- Absorption

SE- Self-disclosure

OF- Openness to Feedback

PS- Perceptiveness

The hypothesized model below, satisfied the criteria for the best fit model. The model apparently showed the interconnectedness between work values and school culture on personal effectiveness. Work values have a direct relationship with personal effectiveness. On the other hand, school culture showed an inverse relationship with personal effectiveness. The best fit model showed that two indicators were included. These results can be further explained by the idea of Juneja and Malhotra (2015) that personal effectiveness alludes to utilizing all the individual assets available to you, abilities, aptitudes, vitality, and time to empower you to accomplish both work and life objectives. The above findings affirmed the theory of Luft and Ingram on Johari Window that outlined self-awareness and mutual understanding between individuals within a group, leading to personal effectiveness. This theory served as the basis for personal understanding effectiveness rooted in school culture, work values, and work engagement.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

As perceived by private school teachers in Region XI, the level of school culture is *high*. Its indicators like *professional collaboration*, *affiliative collegiality*, and *self-determination/efficacy* also garnered *high* ratings. The level of work values is *high* with *core values*, *work environment*, *work interactions*, and *work activities* obtained high rating. The level of work engagement is *high* where vigor, dedication, and absorption are tallied *high* rating. The level of personal effectiveness is *high*, where self-disclosure, openness to feedback, and perceptiveness displayed *high* ratings.

The correlation test showed a significant relationship between school culture, work values, work engagement, and personal effectiveness of private school teachers in Region XI. Work values and work engagement are significant predictors of the personal effectiveness of private school teachers in Region XI. The findings in this section support the literature cited in the correlation between measures.

In identifying the best fit model, using the structural equation model strengthened the reliability and thoroughness of this research because the analysis goes through the steps of model specification, model estimation, and model evaluation. With the five (5) generated models, model 5 best fits the personal effectiveness of teachers. It is the most parsimonious model as it successfully passed all the conventions of a good fit. The success of teachers' personal effectiveness can be related to various factors. Other studies may have proposed these as signs of personal effectiveness in education. It is possible that other factors which manifest more extensively in the respondents were not among those included in the study. According to Chaudhary and Singh (2017), the model fit in the study can positively and positively affect others by passing on thoughts and data plainly and powerfully. It entails arranging and organizing readily available approaches while employing relational skills to aid in the formation of appealing working relationships with others. Thus, the knowledge of personal effectiveness abilities that are dominant in a specific culture and environment would support organizers, administrators, and professionals to create techniques in prosperity in the well-being management of a multi-cultural workforce.

Based on the findings and proposed conclusions, the researcher proposes the recommendations for the basic education private school administrators to continue strengthening the level of school culture, work values, work engagement, and personal effectiveness of teachers by revisiting policies centered on these variables. Today's teachers must be more efficient and committed to their vocation. Teachers must be lifelong learners to communicate teaching with a new paradigm of learning and be adaptive and helpful in dealing with a new set of learners from various age groups, ethnic backgrounds, and a vast range of backgrounds and prior knowledge. This may result in a better school, teacher, and students outcomes.

It is also recommended to create and design professional development open opportunities for teachers to enhance the school culture, work values, and work engagement. Learners' performance is influenced by the traits of a successful teacher. Effective teachers attempt to excite and engage all of their learners in learning. Empowering teachers to enhance the said variables will allow them to show and express their creativity. This can be done through seminars/webinars sponsored by the school administration, a series of meetings, and strategic planning. Further, development activities may center on developing 21st-century skills to quickly adapt to the present time. Additionally, teachers may be oriented on HyFlex learning to connect the future of learning or education. They may be exposed to strategies or approaches in meeting or implementing hybrid learning.

For school top administrations to look into programs on maintaining teachers' work values and work engagement to develop and strengthen teachers' commitment in the institution through the human resource department for teachers to positively reinforce the lowest item of personal effectiveness, responding positively to feedback.

Further, intense monitoring and evaluation may be regularly conducted on teachers' effectiveness. Their weaknesses may be addressed herein, and their strengths may be filled in.

Lastly, for future researchers to conduct more research with other teacher populations, specifically public schools to corroborate the results of this study. They may also employ other variables or factors that may influence teachers' personal effectiveness apart from the variables used in this study.

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